

From Brewery Waste to Biobased, Circular Packaging: Innovation Instrumental to the PPWR Implementation

Evidence on Biobased Packaging Innovation
POLICY BRIEFING

About us

Authors

The BioSupPack project comprises 18 high-level organisations operating in the PHA and PHB-based bioplastics supply chain. BioSupPack is a project funded by the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE/BBI JU).

AIMPLAS Instituto Tecnológico del Plástico: Rosa González Leyba

Agricultural University of Athens: Apostolis Koutinas and Chrysanthi Argeiti

Albstadt Sigmaringen University: Anna Sadzik and Mara Strenger

Centexbel: Willem Uyttendaele

European Bioplastics: Chiara Bearzotti, Estela López-Hermoso, Martina Calò, and Julie Pieters

Graphic Packaging International: Lorena Rodríguez and Elodie Bugnicourt

SABIOMATERIALS: Michele Rossi

About BioSupPack

<https://zenodo.org/communities/biosuppack>

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101023685>

Disclaimer

Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CBE/BBI JU. Neither the European Union nor the CBE/BBI JU can be held responsible for them.

Acknowledgment

BioSupPack has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101023685 under the call "Demonstrate superior bio-based packaging solutions with minimal environmental damage ([BBI-2020-SO3-D4](#))

Licence CC BY 4.0

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.en>

Published on 24 March 2026

Table of Contents

Table of contents

Key Scientific Findings and Recommendations	6
The Need for Biobased and Circular Packaging	8
BioSupPack in a nutshell	12
A Challenging Context for Plastic Packaging Producers	13
Our Recommendations	14
Ensure Feedstock-Neutral Support for Biobased Plastics	15
Enable Market Uptake of Rigid Biobased Packaging Applications	16
Adapt Waste Management Systems to Recognise and Valorise Bioplastics	17
Strengthen Recycling and Circular End-of-Life Routes for Bioplastics	18
Ensure Regulatory Coherence and Innovation-Friendly Frameworks	19
Invest in consumers' awareness, but also workers' skills and capacity building	20
Innovation results - BioSupPack evidence	21
The BioSupPack Technology and Research	22
Production of PHA-based materials and products	24
PHA-based formulations for coated packaging	26
PHB-based formulations for rigid packaging	28
Industrially compostable fibre-based packaging	30
A process for producing PHB-based materials based on brewers' spent grains	32
References	35
Acronyms	37

Key Scientific Findings and Recommendations

Highlights: Key Scientific Findings

- Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) and Polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) can be produced from brewers' spent grains.
- PHA and PHB-based materials can replace conventional fossil-based rigid plastics in food, drinks, cosmetics and home care applications.
- PHA-based rigid packaging is a viable, circular alternative to conventional plastics in multiple consumer sectors. This packaging can meet functional, safety, and performance requirements for food, beverage, cosmetics, and home care applications.
- PHA-based formulations can be used in packaging coatings.
- PHB-based formulations can be used for rigid packaging.
- Compostable fibre-based packaging exhibits barrier properties comparable to those of fossil-based plastics, reduces the carbon footprint, and offers dual end-of-life options, giving consumers choices.
- 100% fibre-based barrier packaging minimises the carbon footprint and provides dual end-of-life pathways.
- PHA materials can be recycled with appropriate waste handling.
- Developed and validated recyclable, biodegradable prototypes can advance the technology toward market readiness.

Policy Recommendations

- To unlock market deployment, European Union policies should support **feedstock- and technology-neutral PHA production**, enable targeted **market-pull measures**, like biobased feedstock targets, and ensure that **waste management systems, standards, and recycling infrastructure are adapted** to the specific properties and end-of-life pathways of PHA materials.
- Implementing the recommendations in this paper would support the objectives of the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR) by enabling the scalable deployment of recyclable, circular, and compliant PHA-based rigid packaging. A **coherent, feedstock and technology-neutral policy framework** would reduce regulatory uncertainty, stimulate investment and innovation, and strengthen the competitiveness of Europe's bioplastics value chain.

Together, these measures would help reduce dependence on fossil-based plastics while advancing the European Union's circular economy and climate goals.

The Need for Biobased and Circular Packaging

The need for biobased and circular packaging

Plastic waste has become a critical challenge in Europe, with the packaging sector at its core. Amid rising geopolitical turbulence and economic uncertainty, Europe is under increasing pressure to enhance the European Union's strategic autonomy by reducing material dependencies while safeguarding industrial resilience. In this context, circularity, the search for sustainable substitutes to fossil fuels and derived petro-polymers, and the bioeconomy have moved to the forefront of the EU policy agenda.

“The bioeconomy represents a strategic opportunity of the 21st century - a driver of green growth, competitiveness and resilience. It makes better use of Europe's biological resources, scientific excellence and industrial base to decarbonise our economy and replace fossil-based materials and products.” ()*

Since 2021, the European Union's policy landscape relevant to sustainable and bio-based packaging has changed significantly, shaping both opportunities and challenges for innovation and market uptake. Sustainable alternatives to conventional plastic packaging are key to addressing this main challenge. At the outset, EU policy was still largely guided by the **EU's Circular Economy Action Plan** (2020), which required Member States to reduce certain types of plastics and encouraged circular design.

(*) A Strategic Framework for a Competitive and Sustainable EU Bioeconomy, 27 November 2025, p. 1. European Commission: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52025DC0960>

During the BioSupPack proposal preparation in 2020, it was assumed that PHA would be considered a plastic-free material as it is a natural polymer biodegradable in marine conditions thus addressing the persistence of marine littering understood as a core concern in SUPD but the later published SUPD guidance stated otherwise which has surely slowed down the adoption of PHA and shall maybe be reconsidered during the impact assessment of SUPD.

During the project's lifetime, the EU adopted one of its most important pieces of legislation in the packaging area: the **Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR)**. The PPWR was formally adopted in 2024, entered into force in early 2025, and will apply as of August 2026, replacing the older Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive. It aims to:

- Make all packaging placed on the EU market recyclable in an economically viable way by 2030.
- Improve recycled content in plastic packaging.
- Reduce unnecessary packaging and packaging waste.
- Introduce binding re-use and labelling requirements across materials.

Several pieces of secondary legislation are needed to fully implement the PPWR, including design-for-recycling criteria, recycled-content verification, sustainability criteria for recycling technologies, labelling and marking guidance, data reporting and methodology, substances of concern, and related areas. Secondary legislation is currently being drafted by the European Commission, with support and involvement from the Joint Research Centre and the European Standardisation Body (CEN), in consultation with stakeholders. Regarding design for recycling criteria, CEN has been coordinating several working groups to develop technical specifications for each material (plastics, ceramics, metals, glass, etc.). A specific subgroup of biodegradable plastics and materials was established, driven by the European bioplastics value chain.

At the same time, EU policy on consumer and product safety has advanced. In 2023, the General Product Safety Regulation replaced an older directive to strengthen safety rules for products placed on the EU market, with implications for packaging that comes into contact with consumers.

In parallel with the waste and safety legislation, the EU policy has moved toward improved product information and circular design through initiatives such as the Digital Product Passport under the broader Ecodesign for Sustainable Products framework, which supports traceability and recycling.

Beyond packaging-specific rules, broader industrial and strategic policies have influenced the context for bio-based innovations. In 2025, the European Commission published the **Clean Industrial Deal**, setting out a roadmap to strengthen EU industrial competitiveness while accelerating decarbonisation and circularity, including support for sustainable materials and technologies.

Most importantly for the packaging sector, the EU also adopted a new **Bioeconomy Strategy** on 27 November 2025 to unlock the potential of bio-based materials and biomanufacturing, promote the sustainable use of biomass, and drive green growth and jobs across sectors. The Strategy lays the groundwork for upcoming legislation that will set the legal framework for future packaging development, including the Circular Economy Act, the Biotech Acts, the launch of the European Bioeconomy Regulators and Innovators Forum, and the European Bioeconomy Investment Deployment Group. These strategic developments reflect a transition in EU policy from early foundational directives to more integrated, lifecycle-oriented regulation that prioritises circular design, recycled and bio-based content, and competitiveness.

Simultaneously, ongoing reviews of standards, labelling initiatives, and revisions of related laws such as the **Safe and Sustainable by Design Framework** (2025), the **Waste Framework Directive** and the **Single-Use Plastics Directive** continue to shape requirements for packaging design and waste management, with future secondary legislation expected to further define how bio-based and recyclable materials are supported and regulated. Combined with changes in the European Commission and Parliament over the project period, this evolving policy context highlights both increasing regulatory certainty and complexity for sustainable packaging innovation in the EU.

Against this evolving policy landscape, the BioSupPack project, started in 2021, has developed biobased and biodegradable packaging solutions for food, beverage, and home care applications. Initiated before the adoption of the **Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR)**, the project has anticipated key regulatory priorities by focusing on material performance, recyclability, and biodegradability. Its results offer timely insights into how innovative biobased materials can support the EU's transition towards a more circular and resilient packaging system.

BioSupPack in a nutshell

BioSupPack is a project aimed to develop and scale up innovative, PHA-based rigid packaging made from brewers' spent grains (BSG) that performs well, is cost-effective, and can be recycled or recovered at the end of its life.

We repurpose brewers' spent grains as a raw material for polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) bioplastics

The 5-year project started in January 2021 and concluded in March 2026. By repurposing brewers' spent grains as a raw material for polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) bioplastics, BioSupPack introduced a high-value recycling pathway that transforms this widely available waste into a renewable, biodegradable packaging solution. Unlike traditional uses, this application aligns with circular economy principles by extending the lifecycle of agricultural by-products and reducing dependence on petroleum-based plastics. It has demonstrated, from the laboratory to the industrial scale, that brewery by-products, such as spent grains, can serve as a reliable feedstock for producing PHB, thereby turning industrial waste streams into valuable raw materials.

BioSupPack has enhanced the technical performance of PHA-based packaging, including its barrier and functional properties, and has evaluated its recycling and reuse options. Moreover, developing PHA from BSG reduces the environmental footprint of both the brewing and plastics industries, demonstrating how industrial symbiosis can lead to more sustainable material production. BioSupPack has brought together actors from the agri-food, bioplastics, pulp and paper and packaging sectors to build a new bio-based value chain. Furthermore, BioSupPack has tested consumer acceptance to ensure that the developed solutions can be successfully launched to market. This approach not only benefits the bioplastics and packaging industries but also provides breweries with an economically attractive waste-management solution.

This innovative approach follows circular economy principles, reducing dependence on fossil-based plastics, minimising industrial waste, and providing a fully biodegradable solution.

A Challenging Context for Plastic Packaging Producers

BioSupPack has successfully demonstrated that biobased materials can be used in different applications with high performance and low costs.

Conventional packaging materials rely heavily on non-renewable fossil resources, limiting Europe's industrial resilience and contributing to plastic pollution and climate change. Existing biobased alternatives often face challenges related to performance, scalability, cost, or end-of-life compatibility with upcoming regulatory requirements. Packaging in Europe is still largely fossil-based and contributes to plastic waste, microplastic pollution, and greenhouse gas emissions, particularly when end-of-life options are limited. With the adoption of the **EU Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR)** in 2024, all packaging placed on the market must be recyclable by 2030, with further requirements on sustainability and design for recycling currently under development.

Europe's packaging and materials sectors face increasing pressure from global competition, resource price volatility, and geopolitical uncertainty. Strengthening European autonomy requires scaling up innovative, bio-based solutions developed through EU research and innovation programmes. The packaging industry is also undergoing rapid transformation due to regulatory changes (**PPWR**, **Bioeconomy Strategy**, **Clean Industrial Deal**, etc.), sustainability commitments, and consumer expectations.

Market and industrial relevance

BioSupPack directly responded to this context by introducing a circular, high-value use of BSG for PHA production. This creates industrial symbiosis between breweries and bioplastics producers, reduces environmental impacts in both sectors, and provides an economically attractive waste valorisation route. The innovation also addresses the "second valley of death" by focusing on scale-up and market-relevant validation.

Our Recommendations

ENSURE FEEDSTOCK- NEUTRAL SUPPORT FOR BIOBASED PLASTICS

BioSupPack evidence: PHA and PHB can be produced from brewers' spent grains.

Recommendations:

- A feedstock-neutral policy framework that supports the use of sustainably sourced biomass, residues, waste streams, and recycled biogenic carbon for bioplastics production must be maintained, based on sustainability performance rather than feedstock category.
- The EU legislation, including secondary legislation (e.g., **PPWR**, **Sustainable Taxonomy**), must not discriminate among feedstock sources, while recognising the contributions of different biomass sources to regional resilience and industrial scalability.
- The competitiveness of the bioplastics sector should be secured by encouraging the flexible and optimal use of diverse, available feedstocks.

RECOMMENDATIONS

ENABLE MARKET UPTAKE OF RIGID BIOBASED PACKAGING APPLICATIONS

BioSupPack evidence: Functional, rigid packaging prototypes for food, beverages, cosmetics, and home care can be made from PHA and PHB.

Recommendations:

- Market pull measures (e.g., incentives, green public procurement, voluntary and mandatory targets) for rigid biobased and biodegradable packaging that are recyclable must be introduced where technical feasibility has been demonstrated. For example, EPR fees could be modulated based on renewable content, or, at least in PPWR, bio-based content could be used as an alternative to recycled content.
- A policy focus solely on flexible packaging should be avoided; rigid biobased applications must also be recognised as essential for replacing fossil-based plastics.

ADAPT WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS TO RECOGNISE AND VALORISE BIOPLASTICS

BioSupPack evidence: PHA materials can be recycled with appropriate waste handling

Recommendations:

- Waste management systems must be adapted to identify, sort, and valorise bioplastics, including biodegradable materials, without disrupting existing recycling streams.
- Smart sorting technologies and data-driven waste management, which enable differentiation among conventional plastics, biobased plastics, and compostable materials, must be supported.
- Bioplastics must be integrated into circular economy strategies, not excluded due to infrastructure constraints.

STRENGTHEN RECYCLING AND CIRCULAR END-OF- LIFE ROUTES FOR BIOPLASTICS

BioSupPack evidence: There is a need for scalable recycling solutions for PHA and PHB.

Recommendations:

- Research, innovation, and deployment of mechanical, chemical, and biological recycling technologies for biobased and biodegradable plastics, including approval pathways for novel recycling processes, must be supported.
- Multiple end-of-life options (recycling and composting, where appropriate) must be encouraged based on application and local infrastructure.

ENSURE REGULATORY COHERENCE AND INNOVATION-FRIENDLY FRAMEWORKS

BioSupPack evidence: Inconsistent policy signals are slowing innovation and increasing investment risk.

Recommendations:

- The frameworks for the bioeconomy, circular economy, climate, and industrial strategies must be consistent.
- PPWR delegated acts and taxonomy rules must not arbitrarily penalise emerging biobased and biodegradable materials at low-to-mid TRLs.
- Pathways for novel materials and processes to reach the market under controlled conditions need to be expanded.
- Sandboxes are a key element of sustainable transformation. They can quickly and safely deploy innovative solutions tested in this project, which serves as a sandbox. They also show how future innovations should be regulated to ensure everyone benefits from them.

RECOMMENDATIONS

INVEST IN CONSUMERS' AWARENESS, BUT ALSO WORKERS' SKILLS AND CAPACITY BUILDING

BioSupPack evidence: Correct disposal and system readiness are critical.

Recommendations:

- Consumer awareness campaigns on bioplastics disposal need investment.
- Educational curricula and professional training must be updated to reflect the needs of the circular bioeconomy.
- Capacity building in waste management, including digital and AI-supported decision-making tools, needs to be strengthened.

INNOVATION RESULTS

BioSupPack evidence

The BioSupPack Technology and Research

This section presents the BioSupPack results, with a brief description of each result and a description of the breakthrough innovation it represents. The text offers information on the strategic action required to bring each innovation to market. Every result is accompanied by the TRL achieved at the end of March 2026.

- 1 Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) and Polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB) can be produced from brewers' spent grains.**
- 2 PHA and PHB-based materials can replace conventional fossil-based rigid plastics in food, drinks, cosmetics and home care applications.**
- 3 PHA-based rigid packaging is a viable, circular alternative to conventional plastics in multiple consumer sectors. This packaging can meet functional, safety, and performance requirements for food, beverage, cosmetics, and home care applications.**
- 4 PHA-based formulations can be used in coating packaging.**
- 5 PHB-based formulations for rigid packaging.**
- 6 Compostable fibre-based packaging exhibits barrier properties comparable to those of fossil-based plastics, reduces the carbon footprint, and offers dual end-of-life options, giving consumers choices.**
- 7 PHA materials can be recycled with appropriate waste handling.**
- 8 Developed and validated recyclable, biodegradable prototypes can advance the technology toward market readiness.**

Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) are a type of measurement system used to assess the maturity level of a particular technology. Each technology project is evaluated against the parameters for each technology level and is then assigned a TRL rating based on the projects progress. There are nine technology readiness levels. TRL 1 is the lowest and TRL 9 is the highest.

Technology readiness levels (TRL). Source, Horizon 2020 Work Programme.

Production of PHA-based materials and products

Biobased, recyclable, and renewable displays that can replace conventional plastic displays. These displays are biobased, recyclable, and innovative. They are based on PHA and can be produced on an industrial scale. Their mechanical performance is comparable to traditional (fossil-based) displays without economic or functional compromises.

✓ For whom are these products interesting?

- Retailers, private-label producers: Pubs, bars, breweries, and soft drink companies.
- Packaging manufacturers, brand owners for food and beverages, cosmetics, and detergents.

✓ The advantages of these products are the following:

The displays are not only eye-catching but also safe for bottles and cans. They are useful tools for advertising and marketing, and they demonstrate sustainability for the brands of bottles and cans.

PHAs material production. Credits: Michele Rossi, SABIOMATERIALS

Potential applications

All displays materials.

TRL 7 - System prototype demonstration in an operational environment

What is missing to bring this result to market maturity (beyond TRL9)

From the analysis of the activities carried out in the BioSupPack project, the main missing steps are two factors listed below.

- The possibility of using PHA that is derived from industrial waste from BioSupPack. The quantity of PHA derived from industrial waste remains low for industrial material production. Moreover, the higher price of PHAs derived from the process could limit their use.
- The need for industrial-scale production: The PHA production system is capable of producing a small batch of materials (e.g., 100 Kg), but a competitive manufacturing process for 3-4 batches of 1,000 kg needs to be developed in the material production process.

Contact for accessing the IP behind this innovation

Michele Rossi

SABIOMATERIALS

michele.rossi@sabiomaterials.com

PHA-based formulations for coated packaging

These are PHA-based formulations for coating packaging. The PHA coatings can be applied to paperboard and textiles. PHA coatings for paperboard compete with PE coatings. The advantage of the PHA is that it is 99% biobased and widely biodegradable. The PHA coatings are designed as a biodegradable alternative to PE coatings on paperboard and to PVC in textiles. The goal is to sell the IP for PHA plastisol coatings through a licensing agreement for Centexbel's patent.

✓ For whom are these formulations interesting?

The PHA coatings can be used by companies that apply barrier coatings to paperboard or by companies that prepare coating formulations for those companies. Additionally, it has potential for companies that coat or print textiles.

✓ Advantages for the adopters

- You do not need to develop your own biobased and biodegradable coating.
- You will receive support to fine-tune the formulation to your needs.

PHA plastisol with blue colourant. Credits: Centexbel.

Potential applications

Paperboard and textiles: PHA-based plastisols can be used as barrier coatings for paperboard in food-packaging applications. They can also serve as coatings and printing inks for textiles, including artificial leather and garment prints.

**TRL 6 — Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment
(industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling
technologies)**

What is missing to bring this result to market maturity (beyond TRL9)

Bringing PHA plastisols to market for packaging requires demonstrating stable large-scale processing, adequate shelf-life performance of the packaged food, and full food-contact compliance, all of which still need substantial validation.

Preliminary recyclability tests are encouraging but not yet conclusive, and additional work on adhesion to paperboard during sealing and cost competitiveness remains necessary.

Contact for accessing the IP behind this innovation

Willem Uyttendaele

Centexbel

wu@centexbel.be

PHB-based formulations for rigid packaging

SABIOMATERIALS has developed a new PHB-based material made from renewable sources by using waste from the beer industry. This material can be used to produce rigid packaging, such as bottles and containers. It is fully biodegradable and mechanically recyclable, helping reduce plastic waste.

The PHB-based material is produced from renewable waste streams, specifically beer-industry by-products. This reduces feedstock costs and the environmental footprint, addressing the economic pressures faced by adopters.

A licensing system for IP generated by SABIOMATERIALS has been set up.

✓ For whom are these formulations interesting?

- Sustainable packaging market.
- Food and beverage companies.
- Cosmetic companies.
- Household products companies.

PHAs material production and rigid packaging prototype production. Credits: Michele Rossi, SABIOMATERIALS.

✓ **Advantages for the adopters**

SABIOMATERIALS' PHB-based materials offer significant advantages over current bioplastics for rigid packaging. While many biobased materials are difficult to process, especially for rigid applications via extrusion, our material has been specifically optimised for enhanced thermal stability, improved melt flow, and mechanical strength, making it compatible with existing extrusion and thermoforming equipment. In addition, unlike some biobased plastics that rely on virgin agricultural feedstocks.

✓ **Potential applications**

Rigid Packaging.

TRL 7 - System prototype demonstration in an operational environment

What is missing to bring this result to market maturity (beyond TRL9)

During the development of PHA-based materials for the BioSupPack project, a limitation of PHAs that derive from industrial waste has emerged. Indeed, the quantity of PHA derived from industrial waste remains too low to meet the real needs of industrial production. Moreover, the higher price of PHAs derived from the process could limit their use.

The actual PHA materials production system can produce a small batch of materials (e.g., 100 Kg). This is essentially due to the form of PHA received from the project. Indeed, the PHA produced in BioSupPack is in powder form. The management of powder hampered the materials manufacturing due to the difficulty of feeding the extruder.

There is a need for an industrially optimised PHA production process to enter competitive manufacturing.

Contact for accessing the IP behind this innovation

Michele Rossi

SABIOMATERIALS

michele.rossi@sabiomaterials.com

Industrially compostable fibre-based packaging

This type of fibre-based packaging is industrially compostable. It exhibits barrier properties comparable to those of fossil-based plastics, e.g., based on Polyethylene (PE), a fossil-based material, reduces the carbon footprint, and offers dual end-of-life options, giving consumers choices. Examples of applications are ice cream cups, ice cream trays, cup lids, and secondary packaging. Other fibre-based packaging can be formed with PHB to replace PE.

✓ For whom is this packaging interesting?

Companies working on developing biobased packaging solutions, compostable and/or recyclable packaging, food and non-food.

✓ Advantages for the adopters

This type of packaging allows adopters to fulfil sustainability claims and goals for compostable packaging, avoid recycled content on the packaging, and produce biobased plastic. Fibre-based packaging can claim dual end-of-life and, in some cases, should be the most appropriate end-of-life option, for example, in **cases of high food contamination or small form factors**.

PHB Fibre-based tray. Credits: Graphic Packaging International

Potential applications

Food and non-food contact products. For instance, ice cream cups, ice cream trays, cup lids, but also secondary packaging

TRL 7 - System prototype demonstration in an operational environment

What is missing to bring this result to market maturity (beyond TRL9)

Some limitations to commercialisation are the following:

- High Production Costs: PHB remains significantly more expensive to produce than traditional plastics, limiting its market competitiveness in comparison with other materials.
- Brittleness and Fragility: As a homopolyester, PHB is inherently brittle and less elastic, requiring blending with plasticisers or other polymers to improve ductility for packaging applications.
- Processing Challenges in Coating: While it offers good barrier performance, applying PHB as a coating on paper requires specialised, often expensive, solvent casting or extrusion, rather than conventional, high-speed coating techniques.
- Recycling: While biodegradable, PHB can complicate existing paper recycling streams, as high coating weights (gsm) used in fibre-based packaging can disrupt standard recovery processes, affecting their recyclability.

Contact for accessing the IP behind this innovation

Lorena Rodríguez

Graphic Packaging International

lorena.rodriguez@graphicpkg.com

A process for producing PHB-based materials based on brewers' spent grains

The present work proposes an integrated biorefinery approach for the valorisation of brewers' spent grains (BSG) into poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) (PHB) via microbial fermentation, with the aim of developing biobased packaging materials. The process integrates BSG pretreatment, fermentation, and downstream polymer recovery within a unified process scheme. Despite its high availability, BSG remains largely underexploited and is mainly channelled to low-value uses, such as animal feed or disposal, indicating significant potential for its upcycling into value-added bioproducts.

✓ The advantages of this process are the following:

- Cost-efficient and sustainable feedstock sourcing: Valorisation of low-cost agro-industrial residues (BSG) reduces raw material costs, mitigates supply chain risks, and avoids competition with food resources.
- Lower technological and scale-up risks: The reliance on a proven fermentation-based refinery concept reduces uncertainty during scale-up and supports a smoother transition from pilot to industrial scale.
- Seamless integration into existing infrastructures: The process is compatible with current biopolymer and biorefinery facilities, minimising capital investment requirements and easing industrial implementation.
- Accelerated market entry: Reduced process development needs translate into shorter development timelines and lower R&D costs, enabling faster time-to-market.

IMIC pilot facilities. Credits: Agricultural University of Athens.

✓ For whom is this process interesting?

- **Biopolymer and PHA producers** – companies producing or planning to integrate biopolymers (e.g., PHB) into their product portfolio for packaging and related applications.
- **Biorefineries** – industrial facilities developing or operating integrated processes for the conversion of biomass and secondary raw materials into high-value bioproducts and biopolymers.
- **Material compounders** – companies specialised in polymer compounding, blending and formulation, developing tailored biopolymer-based materials with targeted mechanical, thermal and barrier properties.

- **Packaging manufacturers/converters** – producers of rigid and flexible packaging solutions seeking sustainable, biobased and biodegradable material alternatives to conventional fossil-based plastics.
- **Brand owners in the food and cosmetics sectors** – companies aiming to reduce the environmental footprint of their packaging and comply with sustainability targets and regulatory requirements.
- **Breweries and agro-industrial companies**, as feedstock providers and potential partners interested in valorising brewers' spent grains through circular bioeconomy and industrial symbiosis schemes.

✓ Advantages for the adopters

This process:

- Uses low-cost waste feedstock instead of sugars or vegetable oils: It reduces dependence on food-grade raw materials, avoids competition with the food value chain, and limits risks to the feedstock supply chain.
- Reduces technical uncertainty and scale-up risks through a validated, fermentation-based refinery process.
- Lowers barriers to the adoption by offering a process framework that can be integrated into existing biopolymers for biorefineries' infrastructure.
- Reduces time-to-market and development costs by eliminating the need for process development and costly trial-and-error.

✓ Potential applications

This process:

- Uses low-cost waste feedstock instead of sugars or vegetable oils: It reduces dependence on food-grade raw materials, avoids competition with the food value chain, and limits risks to the feedstock supply chain.
- Reduces technical uncertainty and scale-up risks through a validated, fermentation-based refinery process.
- Lowers barriers to the adoption by offering a process framework that can be integrated into existing biopolymers for biorefineries' infrastructure.
- Reduces time-to-market and development costs by eliminating the need for process development and costly trial-and-error.

TRL 5 - Technology validated in a relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)

What is missing to bring this result to market maturity (beyond TRL9)

As industries adopt the BSG-to-PHB biorefinery concept, they will need to redesign their process configuration, reformulate materials, or identify alternative feedstocks and technologies. This creates a technological and operational lock-in effect, strengthening long-term adoption.

The most significant steps to be undertaken are listed below:

- Commercial-scale TEA/LCA validation.
- Strategic industrial partnerships and offtake agreements.
- Regulatory approvals and product certification.
- Secured feedstock supply chains.
- Product standardisation and qualification by converters.

Contact for accessing the IP behind this innovation

Prof. Apostolis Koutinas

Department of Food Science and Human Nutrition

Agricultural University of Athens

akoutinas@aua.gr

References

About BioSupPack

The results emerging from BioSupPack are in open access on **Cordis** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101023685>

and on the **Zenodo** platform:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/biosuppack/>

Website: <https://biosuppack.eu/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/biosuppack-project/>

References in the text

First circular economy action plan:

https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy-topics/first-circular-economy-action-plan_en

A Strategic Framework for a Competitive and Sustainable EU Bioeconomy, 27 November 2025: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52025DC0960>

Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR):

https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/waste-and-recycling/packaging-waste_en

Single-Use Plastics Directive:

https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/plastics/single-use-plastics_en

Digital Product Passport: <https://data.europa.eu/en/news-events/news/eus-digital-product-passport-advancing-transparency-and-sustainability>

Ecodesign for Sustainable Products framework:

https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/circular-economy/ecodesign-sustainable-products-regulation_en

Clean Industrial Deal:

https://commission.europa.eu/topics/competitiveness/clean-industrial-deal_en

Bioeconomy Strategy:

https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_25_2819

Safe and Sustainable by Design Framework:

<https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC143022>

Sustainable Taxonomy: https://finance.ec.europa.eu/sustainable-finance/tools-and-standards/eu-taxonomy-sustainable-activities_en

Photos

Cover: Neil916 at English Wikipedia, CC BY 3.0, via Wikipedia Commons https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/a/a7/Spent_grain.jpg

PHAs material production. Image by Michele Rossi, SABIOMATERIALS

PHA plastisol with blue colourant. Image by Centexbel

PHAs material production and rigid packaging prototype production. Image by Michele Rossi, SABIOMATERIALS

PHB fibre-based tray. Image by Graphic Packaging International IMIC pilot facilities. Image by Agricultural University of Athens

Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BBI-JU	Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking
BSG	Brewers' spent grains
CEAP	Circular Economy Action Plan
CEN	European Standardisation Body
EC	European Commission
ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation
EU	European Union
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
H2020	Horizon 2020
IP	Intellectual Property
PE	Polyethylene
PHA	Polyhydroxyalkanoates
PHB	Polyhydroxybutyrate
PPWR	Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride
R&D	Research and Development
SUPD	Single-Use Plastics Directive
TEA	Techno-Economic Assessment
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

